

Adapting a photoperiod-sensitive routine to the INTERCOM model for use in West Africa

F.J. Abamu, M.P. Jones, and M. Wopereis, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA),
01 BP 2551 Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire E-mail: f.abamu@cgiar.org

In West Africa, weeds are the major constraint to rice production. Native African rice *Oryza glaberrima*, however, is very competitive against weeds and research is ongoing to introgress competitive traits of *O. glaberrima* into high-yielding *O. sativa* types (Jones et al 1997). To support this work, the crop-weed competition model INTERCOM (Kropff and van Laar 1993) is being adapted and parameterized to evaluate weed-competitive rice plant types in a prebreeding support project.

The accurate prediction of phenology is the first step in applying process-based mechanistic models as tools for rice research and decision support at the site or regional level. Phenology is important in situations in which weeds compete with rice because competitiveness is affected by the partitioning of dry matter to organs and partitioning is driven by phenology. Phenology in INTER-

COM is calculated from a thermal time ($^{\circ}\text{C day}$) approach that assumes a linear developmental rate from plant emergence to flowering and another from flowering to physiological maturity. Rice development to flowering, however, has been shown to respond to both temperature and photoperiod at specific stages. Thus, subphases—a basic vegetative phase (BVP), a photoperiod-sensitive phase (PSP), and a panicle formation phase (PFP)—have been identified (Vergara and Chang 1985). Varietal sensitivity to photoperiod modulates the duration of PSP, depending on the positive deviation of daylength from a critical daylength value. These were used to modify the phenology routine in INTERCOM in a way similar to that in ORYZA_1 but allowing for multispecies structure, which is characteristic of INTERCOM.

To quantify photoperiod sensitivity and parameterize the routine for 11 rice varieties (see table), data on sowing date, 50% flowering date, and physiological maturity were obtained from plantings done monthly from June to September 1998 at Mbe, Côte d'Ivoire. Data were transformed to Julian dates and inputted into the program DRATES in ORYZA_1 to obtain the duration of BVP, PSP, and PFP for each variety across planting time. In the results, PFP was constant across varieties and planting dates, but BVP and PSP varied considerably. Within a variety, the minimum BVP and PSP from the range were assumed as the value expected for that variety. Then, a photoperiod sensitivity index (PPSE) was derived from the b' -value of fitting a 2-parameter function [$Y = a \cdot \text{EXP}(b \cdot X)$] to the plot of duration to flowering ($^{\circ}\text{C day}$) and photope-

Duration ($^{\circ}\text{C day}$, $T_{\text{base}} = 8^{\circ}\text{C}$) to flowering, grain-filling phase, and photoperiod sensitivity of 11 rice varieties derived for the INTERCOM model from field trials at Mbe, Côte d'Ivoire.

Variety	Default ^a		Adapted ^a				Photoperiod regression statistics			
	E_F	CV%	BVP	PSP	PFP	GFP	R ²	Prob.	PPSE	SE
Bouaké 189	1,831	6	935	491	440	415	0.42	ns	0.135	0.090
CG14	1,417	10	538	309	440	392	0.79	0.05	0.344	0.104
CK4	1,730	3	903	365	440	457	0.64	ns	0.091	0.039
IG10	1,492	33	289	127	440	401	0.91	0.01	1.464	0.296
IR54	1,788	3	943	439	440	438	0.29	ns	0.052	0.047
LAC23	2,005	9	1,099	352	440	407	0.50	ns	0.245	0.138
Moroberekan	1,898	7	1,044	403	440	377	0.77	0.05	0.216	0.067
OS6	1,629	2	821	281	440	387	0.08	ns	0.014	0.028
WAB450-24-3-2-P18-HB	1,304	13	369	179	440	482	0.90	0.01	0.494	0.098
Suakoko 8	2,131	6	1,235	390	440	366	0.77	ns	0.184	0.058
WAB56-104	1,217	7	494	182	440	468	0.75	ns	0.228	0.077

^aDefault refers to the original INTERCOM model, while "Adapted" is INTERCOM with photoperiod sensitivity included. E_F = emergence to flowering (DVS 0.0–1.0), BVP = basic vegetative phase (DVS 0.0–0.4), PSP = photoperiod-sensitive phase (DVS 0.4–0.65), PFP = panicle formation phase (DVS 0.65–1.0), GFP = grain-filling phase (DVS 1.0–2.0), PPSE = photoperiod sensitivity index ($^{\circ}\text{C day h}^{-1}$), SE = standard error, DVS = development stage of the crop.

riod at the start of PSP. A statistical analysis of this regression suggests that *O. glaberrima* IG10 had the strongest PPSE (PPSE = 1.46 °C day; $r^2 = 0.91^{**}$). Three other genotypes—CG14, Moroberekan, and WAB450-24-3-2-P18-HB (see table)—also showed significant responses ($P = 0.05$). The regression, however, was not significant in seven genotypes ($P = 0.05$), suggesting that duration to flowering of these varieties was not affected by the range of photoperiod experienced during the trials.

The parameters derived (see table) were inputted into the original (default) and the revised (adapted) INTERCOM crop model. A comparison (on a 1:1 basis) of simulated days to flowering with actual days to flowering is presented in the figure. Results show that days to flowering across genotypes was underestimated by as many as 21 d in the default procedure and by less than 1 d in the adapted procedure. R^2 for the comparison increased from 0.59 in the default

model to 0.94 in the adapted model, which is an index for overall improvement in the prediction. Further evaluation, parameterization, and module development for phenology as affected by photoperiod are required in rice modeling work that involves the use of *O. glaberrima*. Parameterization and validation of the model for key West African rice weeds are also needed.

References

- Kropff MJ, van Laar HH. 1993. Modelling crop-weed interactions. Wallingford (UK): CAB International, and Los Baños (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.
- Jones MP, Dingkuhn M, Johnson DE, Fagade SO. 1997. Interspecific hybridization: progress and prospects. Bouaké (Côte d'Ivoire): West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA). 231 p.
- Vergara BS, Chang TT. 1985. The flowering response of the rice plant to photoperiod: a review of literature. Los Baños (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.

Acknowledgment

We thank the CGIAR-Canada Linkage Funds (CCLF) for the support given to Dr. Frank Abamu.

Comparisons between observed and simulated duration to flowering (days) of 11 rice varieties at Mbe, Côte d'Ivoire, using the model INTERCOM without (A, default model) and with (B, adapted model) photoperiod effects on duration to flowering.

Virtual rice: simulating the development of plant architecture

T. Watanabe, Department of Information Science and Technology, National Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 3058666, Japan; P.M. Room and J.S. Hanan, Center for Plant Architecture Informatics, Department of Mathematics, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland 4072, Australia

Information on the architecture and morphogenesis of rice plants is important in a range of research fields, such as in the development of ideotypes and direct-seeding techniques and for understanding competition against weeds and compensation for pest dam-

age. Although several simulation models for predicting rice yield exist, there is no detailed model for simulating rice morphogenesis and plant architecture. In this study, the three-dimensional (3D) structure of rice plants was measured and the results were used

to construct a “virtual rice” model that simulates morphogenesis and the development of plant architecture.

The study involved three steps: (1) measurement of the 3D structure at intervals during growth, (2) construction of the